

ALERT SYSTEM FOR ALGAE BLOOM DETECTION IN INLAND WATERS OF LATIN AMERICA: AN ONGOING PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

In a collaboration of several institutions and organizations, this project proposes the use of Google Earth Engine (GEE) to map algae bloom over the main water bodies and reservoirs in LA using Sentinel-2 imagery (2015 to present). The proposed methodology of using Normalized Difference Chlorophyll Index (NDCI) for chlorophyll-a, and TSI detection shown to be very promising. NDCI responds well to high levels of chlorophyll-a and, therefore, can be used as an indicator for algae blooms. The image processing as well as the display of maps and charts are being implemented into a GEE App to be freely available for general public use.

Index Terms— Google Engine App, Sentinel-2, NDCI, monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Algal blooms (ABs) occur when certain kinds of algae grow very quickly, forming patches, or "blooms", in the water. These blooms can be indicators of water degradation and emit powerful toxins which endanger human and animal health. Moreover, they sometimes can cause awful smell that requires more costly treatment for public water supplies, having also a strong impact on sanitation and hygiene [1]–[3].

Considering that one of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) is to ensure quality of water and sanitation for all, knowing the water quality degradation caused by AB is key for its achievement. AB events can be monitored from satellite and an operational system could send alerts to stakeholders to make them aware of a possible occurrence of hazardous species. In this sense, to monitor the trophic state of water bodies is mandatory since eutrophication is one of the main pollution problems of inland water at a global level [4]. For example, AB maps can be used for different applications ranging from urban water supply to fisheries production.

For that reason, a few institutions around the globe are developing mechanism to monitor the occurrence and extent of AB over time [5], [6]. This information can assist health

officials, environmental managers and water treatment facility operators to assure water quality (WQ) for multiple uses. This information can also help the implementation of water quality restoration programs and minimize impacts on fish and tourism industries.

Most of the effort towards AB monitoring has been done in North America and Europe, while in Latin America (LA) such tool has not been developed yet. A series of factors explain this lack of information on LA such as incomplete database to validate water quality products, absence of large research groups for pre-processing satellite images need to generate information on an operational basis. To address this gap, a research project has been approved in an international collaboration (Google Earth Engine and EO Datasience [7]) to build an App that provides near-real time water quality information. The technical strategy is to use the Normalized Difference Chlorophyll-a Index (NDCI) [8], derived from corrected Sentinel-2 (S2) imagery, as the main parameter for spatial and temporal comparison amongst water bodies from different water basins. Then, based on in situ data shared by the project's participants, NDCI will be used to estimate specific information such as AB occurrence, Trophic State Index and chlorophyll-a concentration.

2. OBJECTIVES

Therefore, with the collaboration of several institutions and organizations, this project proposes the use of Google Earth Engine (GEE) to map AB over the main water bodies and reservoirs in LA using Sentinel-2 imagery (2015 to present). The main objective is to provide updated information about the state of water quality degradation (eutrophication level) within the main water bodies in LA. Specific objectives are:

- i. Build a NDCI collection corrected for atmospheric effects using cloud computing (GEE);
- ii. Build a GEE APP to provide near-real time WQ information and spatial stats, graphs, download options;
- iii. Capacity building amongst participants and stakeholder's engagement.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the methodology: Image processing flowed by calibration/validation of predictive models to display results such as chl-a, NDCI, TSI and time-series plots.

3. METHODS

We intend to apply the methodology to areas where in situ data is available for validation purposes, called pilot sites. Once the approach is developed and validated using pilot sites, the method will be transferred to stakeholders at several levels to provide AB information for main water bodies/reservoirs in Latin America.

3.1. Image processing

GEE provide a large collection of satellite imagery, including Sentinel-2 (S2), the current collection with atmospheric correction is COPERNICUS/S2_SR. This collection has been corrected using Sen2Cor algorithm, which has not been designed for water application and show only satisfactory results [9]. Two issues rise with Sen2Cor products: first, the under-correction of red-edge band (B5, 705 nm) which show consistently higher values when compared with in situ radiometric measurements; and the second is the time-series window, which is limited to imagery acquisition from December 2018.

Alternatively, we propose the use of SIAC (Satellite Invariant Atmospheric Correction) implemented in GEE[10], which has shown satisfactory Level-2 (Surface Reflectance) results. The atmospheric corrected S2 imagery will be corrected for sun-glint effects, and then masked for clouds and continental land, followed by NDCI computation[8].

Because the SIAC correction demands high computational processing on GEE it prevents the display of the results online. Alternatively, a NDCI collection will be created in which a single image represents a 5-day NDCI mosaic of the entire LA and stored in the GEE asset. From

2015 to 2020, more than 300 mosaics will be stored summing up to, approximately, 15GB.

3.2. Model's Calibration and Validation

In order to retrieve specific WQ information from NDCI collection, the first step is to calibrate and validate models for chl-a, TSI and AB detection based on in situ database (Figure 1). This process will be, initially, done on a site-specific basis, which means that specific algorithms will be calibrated for a particular database from a water basin or a reservoir. To illustrate the application of this project, we will take the Tietê River Basin (São Paulo, Brazil) as an example. The *in situ* data was taken from CETESB, an official environmental agency in the state of São Paulo[11]. This specific application is subject of a research article in preparation [12]. Using NDCI, a power-law fitting estimates chl-a with a R^2 of 0.78 ($N=186$), and with a decision-tree, one can classify TSI into five classes (Oligo, Meso, Eutrophic, Super and Hypereutrophic) with an overall accuracy of 75%.

3.3. Google Engine APP (Products)

The models validated to estimate chl-a and TSI are being implemented in a GEE App to facilitate non-remote sensing user to access water quality information derived from satellite imagery. App's users can configurate functionalities such as location, date range and products (graphs and spatial stats) to display and/or download to their computer. The intention with this App is to reach a wider public ranging from water managers, agencies, municipalities, and general public.

4. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The first results for the Tietê River Basin present a Sentinel-2 image acquired on Feb 21st, 2017. After atmospheric correction and masking, NDCI was computed and derived chl-a and TSI maps (Lobo et al. *in prep.*). The user will be able to choose any date from the image collection. Figure 2 illustrates the reservoirs Guarapiranga and Billings in the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo City where high NDCI and chl-a (Chlorophyll-a) values are observed. As a result, most of the water surface is classified as Eutrophic or higher levels.

Figure 2: Example of application on the Guarapiranga and Billings reservoirs in São Paulo. a) RGB(432) acquired on Feb 21st, 2017; b) NDCI; c) chl-a estimation; and d) Trophic State Index (TSI).

Figure 3: Time-series plot of NDCI from one pixel highlighted in Figure 2a with a red star.

Besides displaying RGB, NDCI and water quality information, the user will be able to generate time-series plot, such as shown in Figure 3 taken from one pixel in the Billings Reservoir. Time-series analysis can help user to identify trends and temporal patterns that are key for a proper water quality monitoring. For example, in Figure 3 one can notice higher NDCI values during summertime (December to February in the south hemisphere) when compared to winter periods (June to August). Some of this analysis features are being implemented on GEE App (Figure 4, next page), including choosing the location, date, and average chl-a concentration of a given period.

In regards to the third objective of this projects, which is capacity building amongst participants. One of the Project's partners (EO DataScience) have offered 3 online courses on Google Earth Engine (Fundamentals, Machine Learning and App) for the project's participants.

5. CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

Taking the efficacious example of NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) applied for land vegetation, here, the proposed methodology of using NDCI for chlorophyll-a, and TSI detection shown to be very promising. NDCI responds well to high levels of chlorophyll-a and, therefore, can be used as an indicator for algae blooms.

The image processing as well as the display of maps and charts are being implemented into a GEE App to be freely available for general public use.

In parallel to the app development, next steps include the organization of in situ water quality information into a database. We expect to gather WQ data from several Latin American countries such as Uruguay, Argentina, Colombia, Costa Rica and Brazil. With this information, site-specific models will be able to be calibrated/validated. Perhaps, a fit-all model could be applied to retrieve chl-a and TSI in order to allow a large scale spatial-temporal analysis in LA. For example, Figure 5 depicts the average NDCI for January 2020 from Brasília (Brazil) to Buenos Aires (Argentina) demonstrating the potential of cloud computing for large scale analysis.

Figure 4: Preliminary Google Engine App interface developed for detecting algae blooms and trophic state level .

Figure 5: Average NDCI (January 2020) for coastal and inland waters from Brasília (BR) to Buenos Aires (AR).

6. REFERENCES

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